

Toward Generating a DoS and Scan Statistical Network Traffic Metrics for Building Intrusion Detection Solution Based on Machine and Deep Learning: I-Sec-IDS Datasets

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Abstract. In this work, we propose a Denial of Service (DoS) and scan statistical network traffic metrics datasets to build upon Intrusion Detection System (IDS) solutions based on Machine and Deep Learning (MDL) methodologies. We generate the datasets in VirtualBox environment. Two guests are involved and configured to perform the aforementioned attacks for collecting the network traffic. The first one is a Kali Linux VirtualBox machine that executes the DoS and scan attacks against the second one guest, a Microsoft 10. The host machine captures the exchanged network traffic between two guests via Wireshark and saves it in PCAP files. We extract the Canadian Institute of Cybersecurity (CIC)' FlowMeter metrics in Comma-separated Values (CSV) format to label our generated statistical network traffic metrics. Thus, this paper produces the DoS and scan statistical network traffic metrics datasets, cleansed up them before to be free available. In conclusion, this work aims to realise a first training datasets evaluation to design an IDS solutions, based on MDL techniques, upon our datasets.

INTRODUCTION

The latest research shows a huge interest to build an IDS solutions based on MDL methodologies. For designing an IDS upon MDL techniques, the initial datasets play a crucial role. The initial datasets collect the benign and malicious statistical network traffic metrics, which the IDS solutions are trained on. In addition, the malicious statistical network traffic metrics, in the initial datasets, also define the kind of detectable attack classes, such as DoS, SSH Brute Force (SBF), Brute Force Web (BFW), Brute Force XSS (BFX), FTP Brute Force (FBF), SQL Injection (SQLI) and Trojan malware network traffic, which the IDS solution is able to classify. To reach better training performance, the initial datasets shouldn't contain NULL, infinity and labelling error to avoid misclassification errors due to the data incorrectness.

This work aims to realise a DoS and scan open source statistical network traffic metrics datasets for training on them the future IDS solutions, based on the MDL methodologies. To generate the new datasets, we set up the VirtualBox environment with two guests. The one is a Microsoft 10 that is the victim guest. The second one is the attack guest, which is a Kali Linux guest. The attack guest performs three DoS and three scan attacks against the victim guest for compromising it. We run the hping3 and nmap tools for DoS and scan attacks.

In conclusion, the paper evaluates the first IDS solutions, based on Random Forest (RF), XGBoost (XGB) and Artificial Neural Network (ANN), through accuracy, False Alarm Rate (FAR), Undetected Attack (UA) and prediction time, implemented in Python. The first training results are evaluated using all extracted columns. Conversely, we apply the dropped out correlated columns with the 0.7 cutoff. Thus, we re-train our models without the correlated columns. We also evaluate our results on two different machines (a common laptop and High Performance Computing (HPC) clusters).

RELATED WORK

The current advancements design the IDS solutions, trained the MDL methodologies on the most famous and open source datasets, such as DARPA, KDD99, DEFCON, CAIDA, LBNL, CDX, Kyoto, Twente, UMASS, ISCX2012, ADFa and NSL-KDD [1]. The IDS community criticise the above mentioned datasets, due to the them drawbacks [1]. The KDD99 and NSL-KDD, for example, collected old fashion attacks, such as teardrop, warezmaster and warezclient and buffer overflow attacks. The teardrop exploits the IP fragmentation to crash the target victim guest. Conversely, the warezmaster and warezclient employ the File Transfer Protocol (FTP) data and commands, transmitted in clear text, to gain the access to the service. Finally, the buffer overflow overwrites the memory of a program to run malicious code. Nowadays, the communication protocol, such as FTP, and the Operating Systems (OSs) are resilient against the aforementioned three attacks, due to the memory allocation protection, reassembling packet through a stable algorithm and the use of secure channel via Secure Sockets Layer/Transport Layer Security (SSL/TLS). Nevertheless, the KDD99 and NSL-KDD are still used in the latest research to benchmark different IDS solutions [2].

Since 2017, the CIC of the University of New Brunswick provides a new kind of datasets, addressing the lack of the statistical network traffic analysis metrics, the description of the network behaviour and the evolution of intrusions features [1]. The CIC-IDS datasets record, in Amazon Web Services (AWS) Local Area Network (LAN), a new kind of attacks, such as Metasploit modules, Heartbleed, Slowloris and LOIC and so on. Thus, the CIC-IDS datasets are the most suitable data to build the IDS solutions.

Sallam et al. [3] describe the incorrect Internet Protocol (IP) addresses, connection port numbers and timestamp columns utilization to train the IDS solution, due to the use of the adversary of the no well-known port, Network Address Translation (NAT) and IP obfuscations techniques. Thus, we cleansed the datasets, checking the labelling datasets and removing the NULL, infinity, IP addresses, connection port numbers and timestamp values [3, 4] to avoid the models misleading. Conversely, the CIC-IDS datasets contain IP addresses, connection port numbers and timestamp columns that should be manual removed, before the training phase.

SET UP

This work realises a public and open source datasets, collected the DoS and scan statistical network traffic metrics in VirtualBox environment, and aims to build a IDS solution upon those datasets, providing the guideline to replicate the experiment. The involved tools and resources are the VirtualBox, Kali Linux image [5], Windows 10 image, Wireshark and feature extractor [6], as shown in Fig. 1.

FIGURE 1. The involved tools and resources architecture.

The VirtualBox, version 6.1, is the chosen virtualization tool to host two virtual guests. To allow the communication between the guests, the host machine network is plugged the Ethernet cable. We, also, configure the two guests network settings, attached them via the Bridge Adapter and selected the Ethernet host network. We configure the victim guest disabling the Windows Defender and Firewall. Whilst, the attack guest doesn't need any kind of configuration. The Wireshark tool captures and filters the traffic exchanged within the host machine. The IP addresses are filtered to collect only the guests VirtualBox network traffic. The PCAP is the format to save the captured network traffic. Finally, the feature extractor transforms the captured network traffic to compute the network traffic metrics, dumping them in CSV file. The tool is designed upon the CIC-FlowMeter-V4.0 [7] tool, adapting it for our purpose. First of all, we corrected the labelling error, tracked as a typo error [8]. We, also, removed the CIC-FlowMeter-V4.0 training and visualisation platform. To consume the PCAP file, we implemented the Apache file consuming and integrated the configuration files approach, extending the selection of the network traffic metrics in order to skip the undesirable metrics, such as IP addresses, connection port numbers and timestamp columns, that can cause a misclassification errors for the MDL models. Thus, the feature extractor needs a minimal configuration, described as follows:

- configuration 'PCAP source folder' property is configured with the path of PCAP folder for consuming the captured network traffic;
- configuration 'extractors' property configures the extractor configuration file properties;
- extractor configuration properties select the statistical networking traffic that are dumped in the CSV file: for each metric, if it is empty, then it will be skipped in the CSV file, otherwise, it is dumped in the CSV file;
- extractor configuration 'output folder' property sets the CSV output folder;
- extractor configuration 'label' property allows to label the examples.

We adapted the configuration to automatic skip the dumping of the IP addresses, connection port numbers and timestamp columns.

FIGURE 2. The attacks use case, performing a scan *nmap* attacks via the attack guest against the victim guest.

Fig. 2 shows an example of scan attacks. We run six attacks, using the attack guest, against the victim guest. Three DoS attacks are performed via hping3 and three scan attacks are executed through nmap, depicted in Table 1. The hping3 tool floods the victim guest, set the packet FIN (-F), SYN (-S), RST (-R), PUSH (-P), ACK (-A) and URG (-U) flags with packet body size of 15000 bytes (+ 40 bytes of header). The nmap tool aims to gather network information, TCP SYN scans (-sS), OS detection (-O), probing through the open port (-sV), network surveys generating 10000000 hosts (-iR) and skipping the host discovery (-Pn). We run the *feature extractor* two times. The first time, the tool is configured to dump the DoS label via extractor configuration file. Afterwards, the extractor

configuration file is set to dump the scan label. Thus, the six statistical network traffic metric datasets, extracted by *feature extractor*, are available at the output CSV folder.

DATASET DESCRIPTION

Table 1 shows the assigned dataset names to facilitate the downloading and the attack command line to replicate the experiment. Conversely, the other information illustrates the datasets description. The attack class identifies the kind of attack. The rows length is the number of extracted rows by the feature extractor tool and is the total size of dataset examples. The malicious example length is the total size of the malicious examples. Finally, the no correlated number features is the size of the column after the dropping of the correlated feature with 0.7 cutoff. Whilst, the original datasets column size is 78, including also the correlated features. The original datasets column is different from the CIC-IDS datasets, due to the filter application for removing the IP addresses, port numbers and timestamp columns.

TABLE 1. Attacks and datasets information.

Dataset name	Attack command	Attack class	Rows length	Malicious examples length	No correlated number features
dos_fin	hping3 -flood -F -q -d 15000 IP-Victim	DoS	2608	1304	36
dos_sync	hping3 -flood -S -q -d 15000 IP-Victim	DoS	131148	65574	27
dos_rpau	hping3 -flood -R -P -A -U -q -d 15000 IP-Victim	DoS	131148	61789	27
nmap_1	nmap -sS -O IP-Victim	Scan	894	447	39
nmap_2	nmap -sV IP-Victim	Scan	876	438	29
nmap_3	nmap -iR 100000000 -Pn IP-Victim	Scan	1818	909	38

TRAINING RESULTS

We trained our datasets on three MDL models, RF, XGB and ANN. Table 2 shows the training results for the datasets before to apply the correlated feature cutoff. Whilst, Table 3 shows the training results for the datasets without correlated features. The training results comparison is impossible, due to the missing of the research works on our datasets. However, the results are closer to the latest research results, reached accuracy values similar to the other works [3, 4, 9, 10, 11, 12]. In addition, Table 2 and Table 3 depict the results, following FAR, UA and the prediction time prediction performance metrics [4]. The first performance is useful to drive the training phase for reducing the network administrator fatigue. The second one is advantageous to train the model for correct classifying a huge number of malicious examples. Finally, the prediction time shows the near time detection performance. The three prediction performance metrics should drive the training phase to reach the lowest results and, so, the best IDS detection performance. In conclusion, we trained the MDL models, depicted in Table 2 and Table 3, on a common laptop, with 15 GB of RAM and Intel i7-10510U CPU. In addition, we provided to train the MDL models on the HPC architecture, using the University of Geneva clusters [13]. The HPC results are similar to the obtained results on common laptop. We only noted a relevant speeding up in terms of the training models call function, which is not a fundamental prediction performance metric.

TABLE 2. The results of the training phase of the correlated datasets.

Dataset	Model	Accuracy (%)	FAR DoS (%)	FAR Scan (%)	UA (%)	Prediction time
dos_fin	RF	98.876	0.012		0.045	0.028

Dataset	Model	Accuracy (%)	FAR DoS (%)	FAR Scan (%)	UA (%)	Prediction time
dos_sync	XGB	94.239	0.029		0.024	0.006
	ANN	66.794	1.417		40.251	0.028
	RF	99.998	0.005		0.005	0.138
	XGB	99.997	0.003		0.012	0.033
	ANN	66.794	0.280		0.010	0.563
	RF	99.995	0.105		0.010	0.253
dos_rpau	XGB	99.992	0.156		0.003	0.003
	ANN	99.978	0.003		0.156	0.099
	RF	93.816		0.091	0.011	0.013
scan_nmap_1	XGB	99.259		0.741	0.746	0.004
	ANN	49.442		2.143	52.157	0.186
	RF	99.091		0.024	0.725	0.013
scan_nmap_2	XGB	99.145		0.011	0.023	0.004
	ANN	99.240		1.683	0.011	0.197
	RF	99.086		0.735	1.091	0.105
scan_nmap_3	XGB	99.817		0.031	0.266	0.005
	ANN	98.901		1.408	0.761	0.195

TABLE 3. The results of the training phase of the no correlated datasets.

Dataset	Model	Accuracy (%)	FAR DoS (%)	FAR Scan (%)	UA (%)	Prediction time
dos_fin	RF	99.998	0.002		0.001	0.758
	XGB	99.675	0.011		0.003	0.003
	ANN	48.787	50.684		58.50	0.144
dos_sync	RF	99.998	0.030		0.005	0.176
	XGB	99.999	0.001		99.875	0.003
	ANN	48.787	0.180		0.020	0.489

Dataset	Model	Accuracy (%)	FAR DoS (%)	FAR Scan (%)	UA (%)	Prediction time
dos_rpau	RF	99.995	0.101		0.010	0.224
	XGB	99.985	0.048		0.031	0.099
	ANN	99.961	0.045		0.004	0.482
scan_nmap_1	RF	99.628		0.010	0.725	0.014
	XGB	95.878		0.009	0.039	0.002
	ANN	97.926		94.595	0.014	0.143
scan_nmap_2	RF	98.859		0.011	2.206	0.021
	XGB	97.873		0.045	0.001	0.001
	ANN	99.241		0.751	0.775	0.137
scan_nmap_3	RF	99.634		0.346	2.365	0.121
	XGB	99.654		0.001	0.020	0.001
	ANN	91.972		0.007	0.060	0.031

FUTURE WORK

The future work is to increase the attack scenarios, such as SBF, BFW, BFX, SQLI and FBF, to provide additional open source datasets for increasing the attack classes and methodologies. In addition, the proposed datasets dimension is a quite small. An additional future work is to increase the number of benign and malicious examples, over sampling or generating new examples.

CONCLUSION

This works aims to generate the DoS and scan statistical network metrics datasets for the IDS solution based on the MDL methodologies. In addition, it detailed describes the software platform and tools to generate additional datasets, increasing the public and open datasets on the malicious statistical network metrics.

We set up the virtualized software platform via Wireshark, which hosts the victim and attack guests. After, we execute six attacks from attack guest against the victim guest. Whilst, we capture the network traffic via Wireshark. We extract the network traffic metrics via two labelling times, employing our *feature extractor* tool, skipping the IP addresses, connection port numbers and timestamp values.

To complete our work, we generate also the no correlated datasets version, dropping out the correlated features. After, we train the MDL models and compare our results with the latest research. In addition, we re-train our models in HPC clusters, noted only a relevant improvement in terms of the training models call function that is not a relevant prediction performance metric .

The datasets are available at the GitLab repository [14].

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